

A Study on Problems and Prospects of Part Time Job with Special Reference to College Students in Nagercoil

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Abstract:

Being a student at university isn't cheap, but being an international student has even more costs involved. Add to this the increasing cost of living around the world, and finding part time work while studying at university may feel like your only option. You may need to work to cover daily expenses, pay tuition fees, other academic fees, or just to have some extra spending money.

Introduction

Taking up a part-time job while studying will provide many more benefits to students along with money. The part-time job will help them get familiar with the workplace responsibilities prior to the start of their professional career. This will also develop time-management skills. Students who are pursuing their studies can take up many part-time jobs at home after coming from college. We have prepared a comprehensive list of best part-time jobs for college students.

Benefits Of Part Time Job

Better job, but you can also use it to set up your own freelance business and clientele. Working in a part-time job as a student can be quite daunting. You've to think about how it is going to affect your grades and whether the income gained from the part-time job is worth it or not. You must be thinking - are there any real benefits of working in a part-time job as a student. This leads to many students turning down part-time jobs because they are too scared to fail.

As a student, you are young, inexperienced, and trying to excel in a lot of things. One day you are trying to focus on your studies, and on other days, you are trying to be a "real adult" who is living on his/her own for the first time. It can be difficult to manage it all and put yourself in another role - that of an employee.

Yes, you heard us right there are benefits of working in a part time job as a student. When you are in college, a job can look like an enemy, slowing down your progress and wasting your precious time. But the truth is,

working while studying is not as scary as it may seem! In fact, there can be real. Working as a student allows you to take on new challenges and responsibilities. This can Reinforce your belief in yourself to grow into an independent adult quantities. That will serve you will throughout your career. You will be expected to show up on time, dress professionally, care about your performance and take initiative when there are problems.

Job experience is crucial for any college graduate. Having previous work experience on your resume can set you apart from other applicants for a full-time job after graduation. Even if it's for a few hours per week at the campus bookstore or library, having a part-time job will give prospective employers something else to look at besides the GPA on your resume.

When done right, working while studying can make you a ninja time manager. It puts responsibilities in perspective, improves work ethic, and teaches you how to get more done in less time. You learn the importance of time blocking, scheduling, and knowing when to stop procrastinating. It makes you better than most of your college peers who don't know when to stop the fun.

Finding friends outside of class can be a great learning experience. Especially, if they share similar interests as you. Working with others has the added benefit of allowing you to meet new people and letting you get away from routine student life once in a while.

Prospects Of Part Time To College Students

A job prospect refers to a person's potential ability to apply for a get a particular job. It can also refer to the probability of future success in a position or career. Job prospects

are directly related to the career outlook of the position. Jobs with higher career outlooks are often easier to get than those with lower career outlooks. Additionally, a person's level

of education and experience can impact job prospects, as those with more education and experience often have more job prospects than those with less education and experience.

Your degree will have provided you with a whole host of subject-specific and transferrable skills. Despite this it's imperative that you convey how you've gained the core attributes that you think would make you a worthwhile addition to the organization.

Here are some of the most common key skills that graduate employers expect you to demonstrate. It's vital that you understand these skills, and how you can show that you've developed them, in order to write a successful job application

Objectives

To identify the working condition of the sample respondents.

To examine the income pattern of the sample respondents.

To analyze the problems faced by the of the sample respondents.

Collection Of Data

Both primary and secondary data are used for the present research study. The primary data was collected through an interview schedule. A structural interview schedule was administered among the women consumer. The secondary data was collected from magazines, books, articles, journals and websites.

Sample Size

In Nagercoil town there are one lakhs seventy-five thousand women consumer, out of which thousand women consumers are doing part-time job. The researcher has been selected 50 samples for the present project study. Simple random sampling method was used for the present study.

Data Analysis

1.1 Monthly Income

Income is an important determining factor of the family. Income is considered as one of the indicators of economic status and the standard of living of the sample respondents. The monthly income of the sample respondents is given in table 1.1

Table 1.1
Monthly Income of the Sample Respondents

Monthly income	Number of respondents	Percentage
Below 1000	8	16
1000 – 3000	19	38
3000-6000	16	32
6000 Above	7	14
Total	50	100

Source : Primary data

Table1.1 shows that 38 percentage of the sample respondents have the Income ranging between Rs. 1000 to Rs.3000 and 14 percentage of the sample respondents have as monthly income of Rs.6000 Above

1.2 Type Of Work

Part time job is mostly related tailoring, tuition, Account keeping and sales. Following table 1.2 shows the type part time part time work of the sample respondents.

Table 1.2
Type of work of the sample respondents

Type of work	Number of respondents	Percentage
Sales	22	44
Tailoring	4	8
Accountant	17	34
Tuition	7	14
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1.2 shows that 44 percentage of the sample respondents work as sales

girl and 8 percentage of the sample respondents tailoring . It clearly shows

that the most of the sample respondents sales.

A part time position offers flexibility for those who want or need to work but who can't work full time.

1.3 Working Days In A Week

Table 1.3

Working days in a week of the sample respondents

Working days	Number of respondents	Percentage
Below 3	7	14
3-4	10	20
4-6	14	28
6-7	19	38
TOTAL	50	100

Source : Primary data

Table 1.3 shows that 38 percentage of the sample respondents 6-7 days and 14 percentage of the sample respondents below 3 . It clearly shows that the most of the sample respondents 6-7.

1.4 TYPE OF HEALTH PROBLEMS

Part- time working students are prone to various health problems. Depending on the work we do, health problem will occur

TABLE 1.4

Type of health problem of the family respondents

Type of health problem	Number of respondents	Percentage
Headache	2	10
Tension	6	30
Depression	4	20
Body pain	8	40
Total	20	100

Source : Primary data

Table 1.4 shows 40 percentage of the sample respondents have body pain and 10 percentage of the sample respondents have depression and head ache So, it clearly shows that most of the sample respondents have body pain.

1.5 Reason For Work

A part time job can provide you with the cash flow you need to enjoy the college lifestyle. A part- time job can provide you with some extra income so that you don't have to worry about being broke all the time.

TABLE 1.5

Reason for work of the family respondents

Reason for work	Number of respondents	Percentage
Improve self	13	26
Repay a loan	7	14
Earn own money	14	28
Gain a experience	6	12
Interested	10	20
Total	50	100

Source : Primary data

Table 1.5 shows most of the 28 percent respondent can earn own money and 12 percent of the respondent can gain experience, so most of the respondent is earn own money.

Findings

Thirty six percentage of the sample respondents have income ranging between 1000-3000.

Forty four percentage of the sample respondents work as sales girls.

Thirty eight percentages of the sample respondents working days 6-8 days.

Fourty percentage of the sample respondents health problem is body pain.

Twenty eight percentage of the sample respondents can earn own money.

Suggestions

The part time work done by the students should be conducive to life.

It would be good if government scholarship available for part time working students.

Students should be responsible at work and study.

College should also provide some assistance to students who work while studying.

Part- time working students should create their own identity.

Conclusion

One of the best part of working full time while studying part-time is the scope to engage in conversation with college, the space to test once thinking and adopt it. Another huge benefits of doing studies on the side is being able to see firsthand the links between theory and practice, learning new ways of viewing every day routines and commonplace assumptions, and understanding more deeply a little corner of the world.

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